

Biogeographical characteristics of wild chinchillas colonies in Auco, Chile

Amy L. Deane, Save the Wild Chinchillas, Inc. & IUCN SSC SMSG,

amy.deane@gmail.com

Peter Löwe, Head of Development, German National Library of Science and
Technology

Abstract

Long-tailed chinchillas (*Chinchilla lanigera*) are critically endangered. Approximately, half of the population is located inside Reserva Nacional Las Chinchillas in Auco, Chile. The focus of this work lies on changes within the colonies inside the National Chinchilla Reserve; and outside, but adjacent to the currently protected area. In an attempt to better understand the characteristics of the colonies, we utilized digital elevation models (Aster DEM) and optical remote sensing data (Landsat) for GIS-based analysis of the colonies. Changes in area occupied and vegetation indexes as well as the solar radiance for each area was calculated and comparisons were made. The colonies inside of the reserve are decreasing. This study shows that the niche breadth of the chinchilla is wider than previous reports. Basically, there are more colonies now and their average size is larger, with the largest colony doubling since Jimenez's census. In general, colonies have shifted uphill to higher elevation to areas with less vegetation and spend more time in sunlight area during both summer and winter. This study confirms that colonies outside of protected areas are increasing as reported by CONAF.

Introduction

Once believed extinct in the wild, long-tailed chinchillas (*Chinchilla lanigera*) exist in north central Chile (Jiménez 1995). Both species of chinchillas and their range decreased dramatically as millions were exported from Chile for the fur trade (Albert 1900). In Chile, both species are listed as endangered and are protected from international trade by the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), Appendix 1 (CONAF 1988, IUCN 1972). Population estimates of *C. lanigera* vary from less than 1000 to approximately 5000 (Jiménez 1995, Mohlis pers. comm.). Based on colony size and densities reported by Jiménez (1995), approximately 4050 individuals were known to exist in Aucó, Chile as of 1990. At that time, the population was declining (Jiménez 1995).

Chinchillas live together in small to large groupings called colonies. These exist on different mountain slopes, which are scattered throughout the transverse mountains of north central Chile (Mohlis 1983). In some locations, stable colonies have been observed for decades while others have gone extinct (Mohlis 1983, Jiménez 1995). Less than half of the population is located inside of Reserva Nacional Las Chinchillas in Aucó (Jiménez 1995). The reserve was established in 1983 by the Chilean government to protect this species and is administered by Corporación Nacional Forestal (CONAF).

Methods

This study focuses on the spatial changes in the colonies' distribution and the associated topographical variables. A photocopy (1:1) of the official legal map of the National Chinchilla Reserva was purchased from Bienes Raices office in Illapel, Chile. Colonies distribution was obtained from publicly available Chilean Forest Service (CONAF) reports. These images were digitized in ArcGIS 10.1 to create a three polygon vector layers: the reserve limits, the chinchilla colonies in Quebrada Cuyano, directly to the east of the reserve and Quebrada Curico adjacent and south west of the reserve. Layers were added to an existing GIS database, which contains the 1988-90 distribution from Jimenez's original field maps (Jimenez 1995). The RMS factor for all layers was under 0.005. The 2008-10 layer was obtained from researchers. However, the file was corrupt and the colonies had to be adjusted for spatial location. This did not change the extent covered for all but one of the colonies. The colony in El Cobre had to be digitized as it was missing from the electronic file. This resulted that colony being three hectares larger than the original reported size and its replicated size. The digitized map layers for the study areas Cuyano and Curico accuracy is 98%. The replicated colonies under-represented the original data by less than 10 ha (CONAF 10, CONAF 12). This was do to the having to digitize the colonies from digital reports rather than having the original data for analysis.

	Conaf report	Replicated
Curico	398.34	388.51
Cuyano	35.85	36.63
Total ha	434.19	425.14

The first area of interest was to see what changes had occurred in the colonies from the best earliest accurate distribution to the latest available data. Prior studies have not been consistent in their comparisons of the colonies due to the extent of the study areas used (for example, Silva 2010). We used the exact same spatial extent for this temporal study. The colonies inside of the National Chinchilla Reserve were used as a control as there has been no manipulation to these areas. However, outside the reserve in both Quebrada Curico and Quebrada Cuyano, restoration of vegetation was initiated in 1997. Both of these areas are located adjacent but outside of protected areas. In both areas outside of the reserve, illegal hunting of predatory species has occurred. In all, there are three areas of interest: the reserve, Quebrada Curico and Quebrada Cuyano.

Advanced spaceborne thermal emission and reflection radiometer (ASTER) and two Landsat TM5 images from February 1987 and 2011 were obtained from the USGS. The AsterDEM files were used to obtain information on the slope, aspect

and amount of solar insolation for the study area. Landsat TM5 images were selected for the month of February as that corresponds to the study area dry season. The Landsat 5 TM images were used to assess vegetation changes. Images were processed in Multispec, GRASS GIS and QGIS.

Atmospheric correction of Landsat5 images for 08 February 1987 and 25 February 2011 was achieved in QGIS with the DOS1 (Dark Object Subtraction 1) method. To speed up data processing and minimize storage, images were then taken into Multispec to window out the general study area. Images were clipped to the exact same study area extent in QGIS. Using the image calculator in the Semi Automated Classification Plugin for QGIS, normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) were calculated for each date using the Red and Near-infrared portions of each image (Bands 3 and 4). The 1987 image was then subtracted from the 2011 image to produce a change in NDVI raster layer.

All raster layers were georeferenced within three pixels to the existing GIS database. The colony vector data was added to the database. These polygons were used to obtain statistical information for each colony from information in raster layers. The nearest neighbor was calculated from colony edge to colony edge for the first nearest neighbor. Colony population levels were derived based on the reported density/ha calculated by Jimenez's (1995).

Results:

Changes in chinchilla distribution Auco, Chile

This study area included 28 colonies located in the reserve, Curico and Cuyano from Jimenez's 1995 report. Of these colonies, 9 are larger today, 4 are smaller and 14 colonies have disappeared. Based on CONAF's data from 2008 through

2012, thirteen new colonies have been discovered in this study's area. Areas within the reserve experienced a 2% decrease in colony coverage. Also, these colonies are more fragmented than before. However, in both restoration areas, chinchilla colonies have experienced a dramatic increase in spatial coverage. Colonies have increased nearly 2 and 3 fold. Current colonies are in green, older colonies are tan. Personal observation has the population level between 750 and 1500 individuals. Based on maps and the reported density, the current population stands between 2277 to 3790 individuals in these areas.

Population ha	Mean/ha	"-1SD"	"+1SD"
1990's	4.37	3.28	5.46
Reserve	274	1197.38	898.72
Curico	124	541.88	406.72
Cuyano	29	126.73	95.12
TOTAL		1865.99	1400.56
2010's	4.37	3.28	5.46
Reserve	269	1175.53	882.32
Curico	368	1608.16	1207.04
Cuyano	57	249.09	186.96
TOTAL		3032.78	2276.32

The majority of the colonies inside the reserve are small, measuring less than 10ha. Only six are larger than 10 ha. Outside of the reserve no colonies were found to be smaller than 1 ha and the two largest colonies are located outside of the reserve. Extensive colony fragmentation plagues the western side of the reserve. However, outside and to the south western side of the reserve, the colonies are thriving in Curico. In Cuyano, two colonies have undergone

massive expansion. The opposite has happened in the western central reserve area. Where larger colonies are documented in the central eastern protected area, Jimenez reported only one small colony existed during his studies.

The mean data value for each colony was used to calculate statistics to enable comparisons between the two temporal datasets. Basically, there are more colonies now and their average size is larger, with the largest colony doubling since Jimenez's census. In general, colonies have shifted uphill to higher elevation to areas with less vegetation and spend more time in sunlight area during both summer and winter.

	CONAF 08-12	Jimenez 87 89
# of colonies	31	28
size (ha)		
mean	22.39	15.28
s.d.	41.09	24.2
min	0.14	1.42
max	209.97	101.8
Density		
mean	97.85	66.75
s.d.	179.57	105.74
min	0.61	6.21
max	917.56	444.84
elevation (m)		
mean	895.16	886.6
s.d.	122.2	118.42
NDVI values		
mean	-0.02	-0.01
s.d.	0.03	0.04
Day172 sun (hrs)		
mean	8.52	8.27
s.d.	1	1.01
Day355 sun (hrs)		
mean	12.85	12.51
s.d.	0.75	0.98

It has been suggested that colony size and distribution leads to increased chances of local extinction. To examine the distance between colonies, a nearest neighbor analysis was performed on the data and subsets of the data. The distance to the nearest 5 colonies was calculated using ArcGIS online nearest neighbor function. The data was filtered to subset the results and calculate statistics. The colonies in Curico are so large and close together that when considering the entire study area, colonies are more concentrated than the earlier distribution. However, colonies within the reserve and Cuyano are on average actually farther apart than before.

	All areas	Reserve	Curico & Cuyano	Curico	Cuyano
Before					
# of colonies	28.00	18.00	10.00	5.00	5.00
closest	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.19
average	1.19	1.08	1.38	1.42	1.34
stand. dev.	0.82	0.82	0.81	0.84	0.77
Now					
# of colonies	31.00	20.00	11.00	7.00	4.00
closest	0.02	0.13	0.02	0.02	0.19
average	0.95	0.89	1.06	0.68	1.75
stand. dev.	0.68	0.52	0.87	0.69	0.71

Eighteen new areas were colonized between the two sample periods. The distance between the new areas occupied to the closest known area with prior chinchilla colonies was used to calculate the distance for possible sources for colonization. The average distance was 0.47 km from source (minimum: 0.06km, maximum: 1.90km, s.d.: 0.43).

When testing the theory that colonies located farther away from other colonies were more likely to go extinct as suggested by Jimenez (1995), this study area data found the opposite to have occurred. Upon seeing these results, the data was ran again to exclude a colony that clearly was misrepresented in space on one of the maps. Due to its new location, it was deemed extinct in the database tables. The exclusion of this one colony also led to reject the idea that extinct colonies were more likely to go extinct due to distance.

Jimenez	all 28	13 not extinct	15 extinct	14 extinct
minimum	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
maximum	1.27	1.27	1.00	1.00
average	0.37	0.40	0.32	0.31
stand. dev.	0.39	0.47	0.29	0.31

Aspect is however important in our findings, as before chinchilla colonies were highly associated with northern and western facing slopes. Newly colonized areas are on the southern and eastern facing slopes outside of the reserve.

Slope shows the steepness of a landscape. In this image, darker colors represent fewer slopes. Steeper areas are lighter colors. Chinchilla colonies are located on the mountain sides and not the lower flatter portions of the landscape, as reported in prior studies.

The amount of sun exposure has implications due to the changes in the colonies. Newer colonies are located on southern slopes as these slopes have less solar radiation. These two images show winter average time each colony is in sunlight. The top image shows the older distribution, the bottom show the distribution in the current areas.

The amount of sun exposure has implications due to the changes in the colonies. Newer colonies are located on southern slopes as these slopes have less solar radiation. These two images show summer average time each colony is in sunlight. The top image shows the most current distribution, the bottom show the distribution in the early 1990's.

Looking for trends in newer areas versus the older areas, we looked at changes in the colonies for extremes: the coldest and hottest parts of the year. The scale runs hourly based on increasing amount of hours in sun light, from blue to red. Older distribution of colonies are in black. The most recent distribution of the colonies is represented in red (winter, above) and white (summer, below). Basically, chinchillas are colonizing areas that are that on average are in less sunlight. These occur on southern facing slopes.

The range of sunlight hours for each area varies due to location of the colonies in either north/south facing basins or east/west basins. Cuyano is a north/south basin. Curico is an east/west basin. In both areas, colonies have shifted to be in less sunlight during the hottest portion of the year. Inside the reserve, colonies are following the opposite trend and experience more solar insulations during the hot arid summer. However, in general, during the winter, most colonies are in areas with more sun exposure. The DEM (Digital Elevation Model) below has north towards the top right of the model. Colonies are outlines in blue for Cuyano and Curico. Cuyano is the drainage basin to the right. Curico colonies are on the left, bottom of this image.

NDVI was used to calculate vegetation changes within colonies. Changes in vegetation have occurred both inside and outside of the reserve. On average, the entire area has had an increase in vegetation of 10% between 1987 and 2011. In the image below, the newer distribution of colonies is represented by red polygons. Black polygons represent the older distribution. As for the NDVI (Normalized Vegetation Index) image, the greener the area represents an increase in vegetation. Tan areas represent no changes in the vegetation. Red pixels represent loss of vegetation. This is evident along the streams within the northwestern portion of the reserve.

Overall, increases in vegetation have occurred for those colonies inside the reserve and in Cuyano compared to 25 years ago. However, in Curico, the colonies on average have shifted to areas with less vegetation. It is interesting to note that on average the colonies in Curico are in areas with less vegetation than in 1987. In the past, chinchilla habitat has been described as north/west facing slopes (Jimenez 1995, Mohlis 1983).

When looking at the overall area, some trends in vegetation were detected by creating buffer zones within and outside of the reserve boundary. The buffer areas are 100 meters each along the reserve boundary. After 400 meters, areas within each side of the reserve as well as a 2 km distance outside of the protected area were used to calculate changes in vegetation. On the east side and outside of 400 meters from the legal limits the vegetation has recovered the most. The least amount of vegetation recovery has occurred on the western half of the reserve and along the reserve boundary. Along the reserve boundary, vegetation disturbance is enhanced by fence maintenance. Also, goats and other free ranging livestock are guided along the reserve limit. It was surprising to see that overall there is more vegetation recovery outside of the reserve. This is probably due to an overall decrease in free ranging livestock in the area in general.

Citations

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